

Studies on 4-Thiazolidinones. Part-I. Preparation of 2-Aryl-3-[2'-isopropyl-5'-methylphenoxyacetyl-amino]-5H/methyl-4-thiazolidinones

K. P. RODA, R. N. VANSADIA and HANSA PAREKH*

Department of Chemistry, Saurashtra University, Rajkot-360 005

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Some new 4-thiazolidinones have been prepared having 2-isopropyl-5-methylphenoxyacetyl-amino moiety. The Schiff base from 2-isopropyl-5-methylphenoxyacetylhydrazide were condensed with thioglycolic and thiolactic acid. The constitution was supported by ir spectra.

4-THIAZOLIDINONE derivatives have been found to have many physiological activities, viz. anti-convulsant¹, antithyroid², local anaesthetic³, analgesic⁴, sedative⁵ and antiviral activity⁶. Thymol derivatives also possess antituberculous⁷, anthelmintic⁸ and antiseptic⁷ activities. With a view to achieve better therapeutic activity, we have synthesised 4-thiazolidinone derivatives of type 4.

Thymol was condensed with chloroacetic acid and esterified (1), which was treated with hydrazine hydrate to get 2-isopropyl-5-methylphenoxyacetylhydrazide (2). The hydrazide was then condensed with different aromatic aldehyde to get the Schiff-bases (3). This on treatment with thioglycolic and thiolactic acid gave substituted 4-thiazolidinones (4). The constitution of the product was supported by ir spectra.

The schematic presentation of the reaction sequences is given below.

Ir spectra : The ir spectra were taken on KBr pellet in the range 600-4 000 cm^{-1} . The Schiff base gave characteristic bands at 1 680 ($\text{C}=\text{O}$ str), 1 600 cm^{-1} ($\text{C}=\text{N}$ str), and thiazolidinone gave same bands at 1 650 cm^{-1} ($\text{C}=\text{O}$ str of thiazolidinone ring) and 1 590 cm^{-1} ($\text{C}-\text{N}$ str).

Experimental

2-Isopropyl-5-methylphenoxyacetylhydrazide : A mixture of 2-isopropyl-5-methylphenoxyacetate (0.01 mol) in methanol (10 ml) and hydrazine hydrate (0.01 mol) was refluxed on water-bath for 3 h. The product was isolated and crystallised from hot water, (76%), m.p. 78° (Found : C, 64.4 ; H, 8.0 ; N, 12.58. $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_2\text{N}_2$ calcd. for : C, 64.80 ; H, 8.11 ; N, 12.61%).

2-Isopropyl-5-methylphenoxy-N-benzalamino acetamide : Benzaldehyde (0.01 mol) was condensed with the above hydrazide (0.01 mol) in methanol (20 ml), then acetic acid (2-3 drops) was added to it

Reagents : (i) $\text{NH}_2\text{NH}_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$, (ii) ROHO ,
(iii) HS.OHX.COOH .

and refluxed for 5 h at 70-80°. The product was isolated and crystallised from 95% ethanol, (67%),

TABLE 1

Sl. no.	R	Schiff base of type 3			Thiazolidinones of type 4					
		Yield %	M.p. °C	N% Found	X=H			X=CH ₃		
					Yield %	M.p. °C	N% Found	Yield %	M.p. °C	N% Found
1.	Phenyl	67	156	8.95	56	149	7.20	52	139	6.95
2.	4-Hydroxyphenyl	68	124	8.48	54	98	6.50	59	104	6.68
3.	2-Hydroxyphenyl	62	144	8.50	52	138	6.82	54	138	6.70
4.	4-Methoxyphenyl	62	152	8.14	49	121	6.60	48	149	6.49
5.	3,4-Dimethoxyphenyl	54	176	7.49	52	163	6.10	58	163	6.00
6.	Cinnamyl	58	170	8.24	59	130	6.62	55	122	6.52
7.	2-Chlorophenyl	62	184	8.02	48	170	6.57	59	179	6.42
8.	4-Chlorophenyl	60	177	8.04	50	172	6.62	55	144	6.38
9.	2,4-Dichlorophenyl	68	218	7.30	51	209	6.10	58	208	5.85
10.	3,5-Dichloro-2-hydroxyphenyl	63	192	6.92	52	182	5.88	55	178	5.69
11.	4-Aminophenyl	60	220	12.10	58	110	10.48	48	98	10.10
12.	2-Nitrophenyl	58	177	11.70	53	169	9.72	52	165	9.40
13.	4-Nitrophenyl	56	135	11.73	51	121	9.70	56	130	9.42
14.	3-Methoxy-4-hydroxyphenyl	56	140	7.79	53	107	6.40	52	131	6.19
15.	3-Methoxy-2-hydroxyphenyl	52	145	7.76	50	138	6.41	49	117	6.17
16.	4-Methoxy-3-hydroxyphenyl	57	152	7.78	53	118	6.45	52	110	6.21
17.	3,4,5-Trimethoxyphenyl	62	124	6.91	48	192	5.80	56	184	6.69
18.	4-Dimethylaminophenyl	58	207	11.75	56	152	9.78	59	149	9.42
19.	2-Hydroxy-1-naphthyl	51	175	7.36	48	146	6.08	52	155	5.92

m.p. 156° (Found : C, 73.49 ; H, 6.91 ; N, 8.95. C₁₈H₂₂O₂N₂ calcd. for : C, 73.54 ; H, 7.09 ; N, 9.03%).

Similarly, other substituted Schiff bases were prepared (Table 1).

2-Phenyl-3-(2'-isopropyl-5'-methylphenoxyacetyl-amino)-4-thiazolidinone : Thioglycolic acid (0.1 mol) was added to 2-isopropyl-5-methylphenoxy-N-benzalaminoacetamide (0.05 mol) in dry benzene (25 ml) and refluxed for 6 h. The contents were poured in water, and the upper organic layer washed with sodium bicarbonate solution and water, dried with anhydrous sodium sulphate and benzene was distilled off. The product was isolated and crystallised from 95% ethanol, (56%), m.p. 149° (Found : C, 65.56 ; H, 5.90 ; N, 7.20 ; S, 8.23. C₂₁H₂₄O₂N₂S calcd. for : C, 65.62 ; H, 6.25 ; N, 7.29 ; S, 8.33%).

Similarly, other substituted 4-thiazolidinones were prepared. Physical constants are recorded (Table 1).

2-Phenyl-3-(2'-isopropyl-5'-methylphenoxyacetyl-amino)-5-methyl-4-thiazolidinone : Thiolactic acid (0.1 mol) was added to 2-isopropyl-5-methylphenoxy-N-benzalaminoacetamide (0.05 mol) in dry benzene (25 ml) and refluxed for 6 h. The product was

isolated as mentioned above and crystallised from 95% ethanol, (52%), m.p. 139° (Found : C, 66.30 ; H, 6.50 ; N, 6.95 ; S, 7.9. C₂₂H₂₆O₂N₂S calcd. for : C, 66.33 ; H, 6.53 ; N, 7.03 ; S, 8.04%).

Similarly, other substituted 4-thiazolidinones were prepared (Table 1).

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